

The IMLSN Online Resources Website: Sharing Maths Resources

Kirsten Pfeiffer¹, Mike Welby¹, Julie Crowley²

¹University of Galway, ²Munster Technological University

As a reaction to the sudden obligation for Irish maths learning support centres to make suitable online resources quickly available for students due to pandemic restrictions, the IMLSN Shared Mathematics Resources Project was founded in 2020. The aim of this ongoing project is to provide easily searchable, reliable and targeted selections of notes, videos and interactive exercises in key topics in Mathematics and make them available on the IMLSN-website. In this paper we report on the status of this project: the criteria for choosing suitable resources; what topics are available so far; and feedback from users. The strength of this website is that resources are chosen with the Irish context in mind, are quick and easy to find, and that for most topics, interactive exercises with feedback are provided. The MEI symposium provides a welcome opportunity to discuss the progress of the project with the mathematics and statistics learning support community.

Background to the Project

One outcome from a survey on the online presence of maths support centres in Ireland and the UK (conducted in 2018) was that participating Maths Learning Support (MLS) managers “face a number of challenges including institutional control, staff time and skills and a myriad of technical issues.” The authors recommended considering how to be efficient when developing online resources: “... before an MLS practitioner decides to invest precious time and resources on developing their online presence, they should carefully consider why they are developing these resources. Are there similar resources out there that could be used? ...” (Mac An Bhaird et al., 2020, p. 206).

In 2020, as most maths support centres turned to online support due to Covid-19 restrictions, such challenges but also the desire to share resources became apparent. Participants at two Irish Maths Learning Support Network (IMLSN) workshops, held in June 2020 and September 2020 highlighted this issue as pressing¹. The IMLSN committee scoped out a proposed response and surveyed the members of IMLSN about it. The response in the survey was clear: the vast majority said that a curated collation of maths learning resources from different institutions organised by topics would be beneficial for students and colleagues from their institutions. In particular, the challenge for students as well as for tutors to quickly find suitable resources from an overwhelming choice available online was emphasized: “I think it's important that the more basic principles of maths are easily accessed through resources like this.” As a response to this, the IMLSN Shared Mathematics Resources Project was founded. The aim of this project is, by using the existing [IMLSN website](#), to curate and collate a choice of online resources to provide easily searchable, reliable and targeted selections of resources organised by themes. The resources are categorised by subject (mathematics, statistics, applied maths), topic (foundation maths, calculus, linear algebra, hypothesis testing, etc.), and format (videos, notes, interactive exercises).

¹ <https://www.imlsn.ie/index.php/past-events/maths-support-in-covid-times-workshops/imlsn-workshop-12>

With funding from the National Forum for the Enhancement of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education, two experienced tutors were employed to set up the first two chapters of the website. In the initial phase of the project, regular meetings took place to agree (i) on the layout and organisation of the website, (ii) on the organisation of the relevant mathematical topics, and (iii) on criteria for choosing suitable resources. This proved to be difficult as there is an overwhelming amount of excellent online resources available. This initial process was time consuming. However once the group had come to agreement, the development of the first two chapters proceeded smoothly and efficiently. To facilitate continuity of the project, the second author wrote guidelines on how to choose resources for the IMLSN website. Also, authors of chosen resources were contacted, and approval for using their resources on the website was provided. The first chapter on Foundation Mathematics was launched in June 2021. Since September 2021 a second chapter on Calculus is available to use for individuals and for further and higher education institutions in Ireland.

The project is ongoing: the current project team consists of four colleagues from four Irish HE institutions. We are currently gathering feedback from users. Based on this feedback we aim to develop the existing chapters further and to develop more chapters on a variety of mathematical topics such as Linear Algebra, Statistics & Probability, Applied Mathematics, and others. All chapters will be revisited regularly for updating and improvement, taking feedback from the IMLSN community into account. Data is being collected to provide insight in the usage of the resources, and we are planning to conduct further surveys with IMLSN members, teachers and students to gain insights into the usage as well as ideas and suggestions for improvement. Qualitative research will be conducted to find out how students use the different types of resources.

Preliminary Findings from our current Survey

Earlier this year we launched a survey to examine the experience of those who use online mathematics resources, with particular focus on the online mathematics resources on the [IMLSN website](#). The plan is to use this feedback to improve and develop this website further. So far, 8 anonymous participants have filled out the survey. Of those who have used the IMLSN resources webpage, feedback has been very positive (“I think the resources on the IMLSN website are great and should be expanded”). One participant commented that IMLSN resources website could be “very beneficial” for institutions without an extensive pre-existing set of digital resources on their own website. Some maths support centres (MSCs) in Ireland are quite large, well-resourced and have created their own digital repository of resources for their students. However, these MSCs are in the minority. Responses to the survey so far indicate that having a well curated, easy to find, targeted set of good quality digital resources would be beneficial to mathematics tutors and lecturers in supporting their students.

Guidelines for Choosing Resources

Due to the abundance of high-quality online resources, it was necessary to develop and apply some criteria to reduce the number of choices. We established guidelines for the collection of resources and how they should be presented to users. We will outline these

guidelines below. Most of them were based on our own experiences and conversations with students and tutors. It is particularly difficult to choose between the wide range of videos which are available for free. To develop guidelines for choosing videos we were inspired by an article from Guo et al. (2014) which reports about a study of how the style of video production decisions affect student engagement. Their findings suggest that video length was by far the most significant indicator of engagement. (Guo et al., 2014, p. 44). The authors recommend to produce videos shorter than 6 minutes, to display the instructor's head at opportune times in the video, to film in an informal setting, to avoid recording classroom lectures if possible, to use motion and continuous visual flow (for example tablet drawing) in videos rather than presentation slides, to add support for rewatching and skimming, and for instructors to bring out their enthusiasm and to speak fairly fast. (Guo et al., 2014, p. 42).

We developed a directory structure in which we would list all the topics for inclusion along with their order of presentation. For each topic, we wanted a set of notes, one or more videos and interactive exercises for the user to engage with. These were chosen based on a particular set of criteria, which unfortunately were not always possible to completely satisfy.

Some characteristics we looked for in all types of resources included: (i) content that is in line with the "standard" Irish methods taught in LC and upwards; (ii) friendly and accessible presentation to boost the user's confidence; (iii) narrow scope – the resource should focus on the particular topic as much as possible, e.g. deal with adding and subtracting fractions, as opposed to all four arithmetic operations at once; (iv) a clear step-by-step approach from the author as opposed to concise remarks; (v) discussion of common mistakes; (vi) mobile-friendly resources given the modern trend of study via mobile devices.

Ideal criteria for videos included: (i) maximum duration of 10 minutes; (ii) good audio quality and subtitles if these are available), (iii) an informal and friendly presentation style as mentioned previously.

For written notes we looked for: (i) short documents with a soft upper limit of 5 pages; (ii) explanatory pictures if relevant; (iii) uncluttered pages; (iv) exercises, and preferably solutions, to complement the material.

With interactive exercises, we gave a brief overview and explained to the user what they would be asked to do. We also highlighted potential bugs or issues that the user may encounter. The key things to highlight were the facility for checking their method and answers and most importantly, if the exercise has randomised variants that the students can use for repeated practice. It was often difficult to find suitable, or any, exercises so we developed some original ones.

We also included brief descriptions for each resource which outlined what it covered, credited the author, and gave usage notes if relevant, e.g., technical aspects of interactive exercises for those less experienced with computers or the internet; particularly relevant pages in the PDF, or terminology differences between Irish mathematics education and that of other countries, typically the United States.

These guidelines were used by students from the University of Galway for a project where they gathered resources for the website. The students used these guidelines as a template for planning the structure of their contributions, and to inform their decisions on which resources to include based on the criteria outlined above.

Concluding Remarks

Several studies about findings from surveys as part of the SPIRIT Maths project² report that students viewed videos of worked solutions, an online bank of practice questions with feedback and a web portal with searchable topics as the most useful, effective, and favoured types of digital learning support (Lacey et al., 2022, pp. 21/22). Also, according to these studies students have a preference for resources provided or recommended by their own lecturers (Morari & O'Rourke, 2022, p. 18). The authors argue that this suggests that students don't make use of external online resources nearly as much as might have been suspected (Morari & O'Rourke, 2022, p. 19). This is in line with reports from our own students as well as from maths support tutors saying that the amount of available online resources can be overwhelming and finding the right resources can be very time consuming. The project aims to meet all students' preferences as described above. As it may not be possible for lecturers to provide or recommend resources on all material needed for their courses, in particular revision material, recommendations from familiar maths support centres may be a second-best alternative for students. This project aims to provide three types of resources, videos, notes and the preferred choice as mentioned above, namely interactive exercises with feedback. All are suitable for the Irish context and are well organised and easy to find. Lecturers and support centres are encouraged to provide a link to the resources website and recommend using it regularly to their students. We hope that this shared website will grow to be a useful tool for the community.

We value your [feedback](#). Also, if you are interested in taking part in this initiative, please get in touch with one of the authors or the IMLSN. Everyone is very welcome!

References

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² SPIRIT Maths is a teaching and learning project, developed and used in Munster Technological University.